

Growing Infrastructure and Prosperity of Ghana, Africa

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Ghana is a multi-ethnic country with a different populace, semantic and strict groups; while the Akan are the biggest ethnic gathering, they comprise just a majority. Most of Ghanaians are Christian (71.3%), with near a fifth being Muslim and a 10th rehearsing conventional beliefs or detailing no religion. Ghana is a unitary established vote based system drove a both by a president head of state and head of government. Beginning around 1993, it has kept one of the freest and most stable legislatures on the landmass, and performs generally well in measurements of medical care, financial development, and human turn of events. Ghana thus appreciates critical impact in West Africa, and is profoundly coordinated in foreign relations, being an individual from the Non-Aligned Movement, the African Union, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the Group of 24 and the Commonwealth of Nations

Etymology

The derivation of the name Ghana signifies "Strong Warrior King" and was the title concurred to the rulers of the middle age "Ghana" Empire in West Africa — in no way related to the present Ghana, for the realm was further north, in current Republic of Mali, Senegal and southern Mauritania, as well as in the district of Guinea. Ghana was known for its huge gold utilization, and thus was named the Land of Gold by the Arabs during the Trans-Saharan exchanges.

Oversight

Construction activity is divided between several government institutions in Ghana,

These include the Ministry of Roads and Highways, the Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources, the Ministry of Transport, and the Ministry of Works and Housing the latter of which supervises civil works. The ministry of health helps construct hospitals and health facilities, and the ministry of special development is tasked to improve basic infrastructures In a constituency.

Private Participation

In 2011 the Ministry of Finance introduced a framework that established the guidelines for collaboration and leveraged public assets and private resources to accelerate the development of infrastructure and services. The private sector is defined as Organizations that have a core strategy and mission to engage in profit-seeking activities through the production of goods, provision of services, and/or commercialization. Includes financial institutions and intermediaries, large corporations, micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises, co-operatives, individual entrepreneurs, and farmers which operate in the formal and informal sectors. Thus, the private sector is simply made up of individuals and or organizations engaged in rent seeking activities that relies on governments or states to create an enabling business environment for their successful operations. In this respect, interdependence between the private sector and state or government is created since governments need the private sector to complement its efforts in the creation of jobs, revenue generation, provision of infrastructure and other services to its citizenry. The Ghana Infrastructure Investment Fund is a critical player in managing PPPs. It was established in 2014 with a mandate to coordinate and provide financial resources for investment in a diversified portfolio of infrastructure projects, as well as generate returns for shareholders.

The GIIF taps both public and private funding from investors at home and abroad to carry out its mandate.

Performance & Size

Construction offers substantial potential to propel economic growth and employment.

Construction accounted for 7.1% of GDP in 2018, according to the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS). That year the sector contributed GHS19.7bn (\$3.82bn) to GDP, up from GHS19.4bn (\$3.76bn) in 2017 and nearly double the GHS10.6bn (\$2.1bn) seen in 2010. This expansion is expected to continue into the future, with credit ratings agency Fitch citing strong fundamentals in its July 2019 projection that the industry would grow by 3.4% in 2019 and 5.8% in 2020, albeit down from the firm's original forecast of 7.3% and 7.4%, respectively. According to the 2017 "Labour Force Report" from the GSS, construction employed over 316,000 people, constituting around 3% of the labor force. It also employed more than 4.4% of the country's youth. Construction increases industrialization and creates indirect employment opportunities in the manufacturing, mining and agriculture sectors in Ghana.

Budget

The 2020 budget highlighted the acceleration of infrastructure development as a key area of focus. It earmarked GHS5.1bn (\$987.9m), or 11% of the total budget for administration, economy, infrastructure, social services and public safety, to infrastructure development, up from the GHS4.6bn (\$891m) allotted in 2019.

Regulatory Support

Regulatory Support means helping respond to data requests or other information requests from governmental bodies or third parties in regulatory matters; helping prepare testimony; and helping prepare filings in regulatory proceedings. Recent policy and regulatory measures provide the impetus for further maturation of the

sector and broader socio-economic development. In September 2018 Mavis Hawa Koomson, the minister of special development initiatives, signaled the government's strong support for the creation of the Construction Industry Development Authority at the 10th annual conference of the Association of Building and Civil Engineering Contractors of Ghana. The CIDA would act as an overarching regulator and supporter of the construction industry.

Water In Ghana

While some African countries suffer from a lack of water, Ghana suffers from too much polluted water, problems like deforestation have contributed to

contaminated groundwater, the largest source of pollution sources have been tied to small-scale, illegal gold mining. Ghana is Africa's largest producer of gold, and it is estimated that about 35% of the precious metal comes from these illegal, small-scale operations. Pollution from the mining process has contaminated water sources across Ghana with toxic heavy metals, such as mercury and lead. These heavy metals are difficult to filter out even when using a water treatment facility, and cannot be boiled out by

families collecting the polluted water. In Ghana's rural areas, just 11 percent of the population has access to safely managed drinking water. In urban areas, the increase in water pollution coupled with rapid population growth has led to poor water, sanitation and hygiene. Just 13 percent of Ghana's 31 million people have access to safely managed sanitation services, and 22 percent don't have access to basic hygiene services like handwashing facilities with soap and water.

For families in Ghana, finding a clean, safe source for water is vital to their survival. The construction of wells in water-scarce communities relieve families of the search for water sources, saving families as much as 200 hours of time per

year. This is especially important for the women and girls overwhelmingly responsible for water retrieval: instead of dedicating most of their day towards fetching water, they can participate in other activities like employment, church, education, leisure, and simply being a kid.

Clean water also acts as a steppingstone towards community development as a whole. It makes sense: when community members aren't sick, children can stay in school longer, families can devote more time towards economic activities, and churches can grow their congregation and reach more lives than before. Once the basic need of clean water is met, communities can come together and build each other up.

The benefits of living in an underdeveloped country like Ghana for every smart entrepreneur

Ghana being underdeveloped represented a great deal of points of interest to the up and coming business visionary. I proposed this thought, over the long haul, we would do better at odds of making it in Ghana than somewhere else, in light of the fact that Ghana was underdeveloped.

But let's start things off the right way, is Ghana underdeveloped?

Many of the underlying causes of developed and underdeveloped nations are rooted in the long history of the development of such nations and include social, cultural and economic variables, historical and political elements, international relations, and geographical factors. A developing country is a sovereign state with a less developed industrial base and a lower Human Development Index relative to other countries. The Human Development Index is a statistic composite index of life expectancy, education, and per capita income indicators, which are used to rank countries into four tiers of human development.

Ghana is considered to be a less economically developed country mainly because of the fact that it is not very rich. Perhaps the best measure of this is the fact that its per capita GDP (when adjusted to take into account what things cost in the country) is well below the world average. Ghana's GDP per capita is 6622.50 GHS (2016). Ghana is a least Developed country because of the nature of its economy.

56 percent of the Ghanaian population are involved in agriculture. This is not a very efficient sector of the economy and only 30% of Ghana's GDP comes from the labor of that 56%.which makes Ghana an underdeveloped country.

Are there really benefits to living in an underdeveloped country like Ghana?

Underdeveloped nations are regularly ripe ground for individuals with instruction, vision and access to capital, to make something positive.

Infrastructural advancements are being made at a sensational pace. Numerous individuals are amazed at the pace of advancement and enhancements in ways of life in such huge numbers of nations they have up to this point apparent as 'underdeveloped'. There is a peaceful 'improvement upset' occurring that very few individuals living in the West know about. It might possibly hit them if their own situations on the planet start to slide thus. As these economies begin to get up to speed, it is extremely energizing occasions and they offer the opportunity for individuals to find success with their thoughts and yearnings. Likewise, heaps of these nations have an enormous diaspora in the West and they are taking care of their vitality back home as data, inventiveness and capital. The underdeveloped idea of Ghana likewise makes an extraordinary possibility for business people to enhance without any problem.

About Ghana

Ghana is a country located in Western Africa. Neighboring countries include Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Togo, and the Gulf of Guinea. Lake Volta, the largest artificial lake in the world, is located entirely within Ghana. The government system is a presidential republic; the chief of state and head of government is the president. Ghana has a mixed economic system, which includes some private freedom combined with weak centralized economic planning and government regulation.

Ghana is a member of the Economic Community of West African States. Ghana was the first place in sub-Saharan Africa where Europeans arrived to trade - first in gold, later in slaves. It was also the first black African country to gain freedom from its colonial masters in 1957.

History of Ghana

The Portuguese reached what is now Ghana in 1482. They found it was a rich source of gold. So much so that the area was called the Gold Coast. The Portuguese built forts on the Gold Coast and during the 16th century, they traded with the native peoples.

However in the early 17th century, the Portuguese lost their position to the Dutch, who captured their forts. Later in the 17th century, the British and the Danes also built forts on the Gold Coast. At first, gold was the main export from the area but by the late 17th century it was slaves. Slavery was not new in Africa (or any other continent). However, the trans-Atlantic slave trade was on a huge scale. African chiefs sold slaves to the Europeans in return for guns, tobacco, and alcohol. During the 18th century, vast numbers of slaves were transported across the Atlantic. However, in the late 18th century public opinion in Europe turned against the slave trade. The first country to abolish the slave trade was Denmark in 1803. Britain followed in 1807. British influence gradually grew in Ghana during the 19th century. The British fought a series of wars with the Ashanti. Meanwhile the British bought the Danish and Dutch forts. Finally, on 24 July 1874, the coastal

area of Gold Coast was declared a crown colony. British rule was later extended inland. In 1901 Ashanti was declared a crown colony. The area further north was made a British protectorate.

Challenges

Malaria still remains a public health concern as it is the leading cause of morbidity in Ghana. There are still challenges in meeting the goal of reducing maternal mortality ratio to the expected 185 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births by 2015. Also Ghana's forest cover continues to decline rapidly. The agriculture sector, particularly the food crop sub-sector, continues to rely on rain-fed agriculture and the adoption of limited modern agricultural techniques.

The business climate in Ghana is still weak and continues to hold back productive investment particularly in the area of manufacturing. The business community is often constrained by limited and unreliable supply of energy and affordable finance especially for SMEs to enable them to expand production, create jobs and improve incomes of workers.

Successes

First President of Ghana, as prosperity grew in Ghana after independence. Once an African success story built on gold, oil and cocoa, Ghana leveraged its natural resources to produce strong economic growth in the early years of this century. It met the millennium development goal of halving poverty rates by 2015, and was hailed as a model of political stability after peaceful elections. Ghana is the first country in Sub-Saharan Africa to achieve the Millenium Development Goal 1, which is the target of halving extreme poverty.

Figure 1 Kwame NKrumah

Ghana has made real progress in good governance, youth and gender empowerment. Important pieces of relevant legislation have been enacted and institutional arrangements improved to promote inclusive society.

Government for instance has enacted the Domestic Violence and Disability Laws, established Domestic Violence Victim Support Units

and the implementation of the National Social Protection Strategy. Over the last decade, Ghana has enjoyed increasingly stable and deepening democratic governance. Four successful elections in 2000, 2004, 2008 and 2012 have strengthened the effectiveness of key national institutions, enhanced investor confidence and anchored the new economy in an environment for positive growth. Ghana has a high-profile peacekeeping role; troops have been deployed in Ivory Coast, Liberia, Sierra Leone and DR Congo.

Video of Ghana Independence 1957

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/transcoded/5/5a/Ghana_%281957-03-07_A_New_Nation%29.ogv/Ghana_%281957-03-07_A_New_Nation%29.ogv.480p.webm

Presidents of Ghana Africa 1-4th

